

PERFORMANCE OF PRICES OF GUAR GUM TRADED AT NCDEX, MUMBAI

S.S. Wagh*, S V Warade**, V S Khawale*** and N T Bagde****

* Master of Business Administration in Agri-Business Management, School of Agri-business Management, Nagpur

** Associate Professor (CAS), School of Agri-Business Management, Nagpur

*** Director, School of Agri- Business Management, Nagpur

**** I/C Professor Section of Agricultural Economics and Statistics, College of Agriculture, Nagpur

siddhantwagh161199@gmail.com

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Abstract

The research focused on the analysis of the performance of Guar Gum traded at the National Commodity & Derivatives Exchange (NCDEX) in India. The research highlights the role of futures markets in stabilizing prices, risk management, and price discovery for these agricultural commodities. The research examines data from 2015-2023, analyzing daily closing spot and futures prices for the selected commodity. By using statistical tools like the Compound Growth Rate (CGR) and Coefficient of Variation (CV), the study provides insights into market volatility and price trends. Compound growth rate of spot price, future price and delivered quantity is 0.40, 0.40, -1.11 respectively. Both spot and future prices of Guar Gum grew significantly, while delivery rates declined. Price volatility was assessed using the Coefficient of Variation (CV) and the Cuddy Della Index, revealing moderate variability in spot and future prices but high variability in delivery. Regression Coefficient of area is -1.22 and t value is -1.86, regression coefficient of production is 1.81 and t value is 1.44, suggesting that the effect of area and production on spot prices at AGMARK is not statistically significant. The negative coefficient suggests that an increase in area is associated with a decrease in spot prices. At NCDEX, regression coefficient for area is -1.32 and t value is -0.69 and the regression coefficient for production is 2.63, t-value for production is 0.71. that shows area nor production variables show a statistically significant impact on Guar gum NCDEX prices. The overall findings provide insights into price movements and market stability within the Guar Gum markets during the study period.

Keywords: NCDEX, Guar gum, Spot price, Future price, delivered quantity, Compound Growth Rate (CGR), Coefficient of Variation (CV), Cuddy Della Index, Price volatility etc.

Introduction and Objectives

Guar is one of the vital crop in Indian agriculture. Guar, or cluster bean (*Cyamopsis tetragonoloba*), is indigenous to India and has been grown for centuries. Historically, it has been used as green manure in agriculture, as a vegetable, and as feed for cattle.

Guar gum, derived from guar plant seeds, is a key agricultural product used in the food industry and for hydraulic fracturing in oil and gas. India produces 80-90% of the world's guar gum, with major cultivation in Rajasthan, Haryana, Punjab, and Gujarat, covering 2.5-3 million hectares. The average yield is 400-600 kg/ha, higher with improved practices. India exports 70-80% of its guar gum, primarily to the U.S., China, Germany, and UAE, with annual exports ranging from 200,000 to 300,000 metric tons. Guar gum's global demand is shaped by industrial needs and market conditions.

Commodity markets have played a key role in economic growth and development of country. The organized trading concept in commodities evolved in the middle of the 19th century.

Farmers (sellers) and dealers (buyers) began agreeing to exchange produce for cash at a future date, leading to the development of "futures" contracts. In these agreements, producers committed to selling their crops, like wheat, at a set price on a future date. This provided farmers with certainty about their income and allowed dealers to plan for costs. The arrangement was beneficial for both parties and quickly gained popularity, with contracts often being traded before the delivery date. Commodity futures trading in India dates back nearly as long as in the United States. The country's first organized futures market, the Bombay Cotton Trade Association Ltd., was established in 1875. Futures trading in oilseeds began with the formation of the Gujarati Vyapari Mandali in 1900, while gold futures started in Mumbai in 1920. By the early 20th century, several commodity exchanges were active, trading in items like jute, pepper, turmeric, potatoes, and sugar.

The National Commodities and Derivatives Exchange Limited (NCDEX), established on April 23, 2003, is India's largest agricultural commodity exchange, holding 75% of the contract cultivation market as of March 2021. Regulated by SEBI, NCDEX offers a range of products like commodity futures, options, and forwards for 11 agricultural commodities. It plays a key role in price discovery, providing farmers

NAAS Rating – 04.17

with transparent market data to optimize selling times and helping investors reduce volatility. Futures contracts on NCDEX allow hedging against price fluctuations, ensuring price stability and reducing income risks. Centralized trading on NCDEX also lowers transaction costs, promoting stability and fair pricing.

In India, futures trading is now allowed for many agriculture commodities, most of which are traded through various exchanges. Since the Indian economy relies heavily on agriculture, the agricultural commodity market plays a major role. Allowing futures trading on national exchanges brings more liquidity, helps with price discovery, and offers better risk management. National Commodity Exchanges are also attracting new investors, creating more opportunities for trading and business growth. These exchanges must focus on providing accurate price information, good investment options, and strong risk management. Guar complex is an important commodity on NCDEX. On the NCDEX, the guar complex demonstrated strong performance, accounting for 50% of the Exchange's total turnover in FY 2022-23. Specifically, Guar Seed and Guar Gum contributed 26% and 24%, respectively, to the overall turnover.

This study aims to analyze how agricultural commodities are performing on National Commodity & Derivatives Exchange (NCDEX) in India

Objectives of the study

The study was selected keeping in view the above facts, an attempt is made to critically assess the performance analysis of NCDEX futures and spot trading in Guar Gum with the following specific objectives:

To study the prices & quantity traded through NCDEX.

To analyze the future price and spot price variation of selected commodity (Guar gum).

To examine the impact of arrivals on prices.

Materials and Methods

For the present study, Guar gum is a major agricultural commodity currently traded at National Commodity & Derivatives Exchange (NCDEX) were selected. Secondary data on futures price, spot prices, and delivered quantity of Guar gum traded on NCDEX were collected from the official web site of Forward Market Commission (FMC), Mumbai and respective web sites of the National Level Commodity Exchanges in India for the period 2015 to 2023.

Analytical tool

For the purpose of accomplishing the objectives of the study, data were analyzed using the following techniques.

Compound Growth Rate (CGR) Estimation:

For achieving the first objective, which is to study the prices and quantities traded through NCDEX, the Compound Growth Rate (CGR) was calculated using a regression model. The fundamental equation for estimating CGR is:

$$y = ab^t$$

Where,

y = prices or quantities of selected commodity

a = Intercept

t = The period over which growth is measured.

b = Coefficient

$$\text{CGR} = [\text{Antilog}(\log b - 1)] \times 100$$

The t test was applied to test of significance

Coefficient of Variation

For achieving the second objective, which is to analyse the future and spot price variations of selected commodity (Guar Gum), the Coefficient of Variation (CV) is used as a key metric.

The Coefficient of Variation is calculated using the formula

$$CV = \frac{\sigma}{\mu}$$

Where:

σ (Standard Deviation)

μ (Mean)

Cuddy Della Index

Table 1: Compound Growth Rate of Guar gum in NCDEX (2015–23)

Sr. No.	Particular	Compound Growth Rate	t value
1	Spot price	0.40***	4.11
2	Future price	0.40***	4.19
3	Delivery	-1.11***	-5.22

Note: ***Significant at 1% level.

The spot price of Guar gum has a positive CGR of 0.40. The t-test value of 4.11 is significantly higher. This suggests that the growth rate is statistically significant. Similar to the spot price, the future price also exhibits a positive CGR of 0.40. The t-value of 4.19 is slightly higher than the spot price's t-value. This confirms that the growth in future prices is also statistically significant and reliable. The delivery CGR is negative at -1.11, which indicates a decrease in the delivery rates of Guar gum. This is a significant drop. The t-value of -5.22 is suggesting that the decline in delivery rates is statistically significant.

Both the spot and future prices of Guar gum have shown substantial and statistically significant over the period from 2015 to 2023. Conversely, the delivery rates of Guar gum have experienced a significant and

substantial decline. This decline is also statistically significant, suggesting a strong and consistent downward trend.

For further analyse the stability of price variations in the selected commodity (Guar Gum), the Cuddy Della Index is employed. This index is particularly useful for assessing the reliability of the Coefficient of Variation (CV) when analysing time series data.

The Cuddy Della Index is calculated using the formula:

$$\text{Cuddy - Della Valle Index (\%)} = C.V. * \sqrt{1 - R^2}$$

4 Regression Analysis

For achieving the third objective, which is to examine the impact of arrivals on futures prices for selected commodity (Guar Gum), a multiple regression analysis is conducted. This statistical technique will help quantify the relationship between the arrivals of these commodities and their prices.

The regression model is specified as follows:

$$y = a + b_1X_1 + b_2X_2$$

Where:

y = The dependent variable (price)

a = Intercept

X₁ = The area under cultivation for the Guar seed.

X₂ = the production of the Guar seed

Results and Discussion**Growth in Quantity and Prices of Selected Commodity at NCDEX**

For estimate the growth in Guar gum trade we used Compound Growth Rate (CGR) matric. The data provided in table 1 shows the Compound Growth Rates (CGR) and t-values for different aspects of Guar gum trading on the NCDEX (National Commodity and Derivatives Exchange) from 2015 to 2023.

substantial decline. This decline is also statistically significant, suggesting a strong and consistent downward trend.

Variation in future price, spot price & delivery:

The second objective, which is to analyse the future and spot price variations of selected commodity (Guar gum), the Coefficient of Variation (CV) is employed as a key metric. CV, which measures price volatility, is calculated by dividing the standard deviation of prices by the mean price. This provides a clear understanding of price fluctuations relative to the average price over the study period, helping assess market volatility. Additionally, the Cuddy Della Index is used to further refine the analysis by accounting for the variability not explained by the regression model, offering deeper insights into market stability for Guar gum.

Table 2: Coefficient of Variation and Cuddy Della Index of Guam gum (2015-23)

Year	Spot price		Future price		Delivery	
	C.V.	CDI	C.V.	CDI	C.V.	CDI
2015	20.46	9.51	20.70	18.73	33.66	31.33
2016	7.55	6.44	6.97	5.90	68.80	67.83
2017	10.31	7.94	9.94	7.48	53.70	52.97
2018	7.59	7.58	7.74	7.73	57.33	56.96
2019	6.13	4.51	6.19	4.45	44.16	43.15
2020	10.95	10.82	10.48	10.34	38.51	35.28
2021	28.81	13.79	29.02	13.75	50.39	40.53
2022	11.78	10.94	12.15	11.19	41.95	41.64
2023	6.56	6.05	6.83	6.12	61.74	56.12

From table 2, the coefficient of variation (CV) for spot prices indicates moderate variability, with the highest CV recorded in 2021 i.e. 28.81 and

lowest CV recorded in 2016 i.e. 6.13. Future price CV is slightly lower, suggesting less relative variability, with the highest CV recorded in 2021

i.e. 29.02 and lowest CV recorded in 2016 i.e. 6.19, while delivery CV shows the highest variability, particularly notable in 2016 (67.83).

Volatility Analysis (Cuddy Della Index):

The volatility index for spot prices fluctuates over the years, with peaks observed in 2021 (13.79) and 2021 (10.82), and lower values in 2019 (6.19) and 2023 (6.83) indicating periods of more stability. Future prices generally exhibit higher volatility compared to spot prices, especially in 2015 (18.73) and 2021(13.75) while lowest volatility in 2019 (4.45). Delivery values show high volatility across the years, with extreme values in 2016 (67.83) lowest in 2015 (31.33), reflecting substantial fluctuations.

Inter-relationships:

There is a consistent correlation between spot and future prices, where future prices tend to follow spot prices but with less variability. However, there is no direct linear relationship between spot prices and delivery values; delivery values exhibit high variability independently of spot price trends. Similarly, delivery variations do not show a consistent pattern relative to future prices.

Price Variation in spot price demonstrates substantial upward movement accompanied by high variability, with notable fluctuations occurring in 2015 and 2021. Future prices generally follow the trend of spot prices but exhibit slightly less volatility and tend to lag behind in their movements. Delivery values show significant variability and exhibit a low correlation with both spot and future prices. This suggests that factors influencing delivery are distinct from those affecting price changes, indicating that delivery metrics are driven by different variables. Volatility of both spot and future prices experience periods of high and low volatility, reflecting their fluctuating nature. In contrast, the delivery metric displays the highest level of volatility, characterized by frequent and substantial changes in delivery values.

Table 3: Estimated spot market price of Guar seed from AGMARK (2015 – 2023)

Year	Original Price	Estimated Price
2015-16	3662.91	3558.66
2016-17	3080.28	3626.68
2017-18	3431.04	3422.63
2018-19	3998.21	3428.53
2019-20	3894.08	4206.09
2020-21	3588.64	4341.25
2021-22	4589.64	4404.16
2022-23	5306.45	4563.24

Table 4: Impact of Area and Production on Guar seed AGMARK Prices

Sr. No.	Particular	Regression Coefficient	t Value
1	Intercept	5293.27	6.26
2	Area	-1.22	-1.86
3	Production	1.81	1.44

In 2019-20 the estimated prices are 3894.08 and original price is 4206.09. In 2020-21 estimated prices is 3588.64 and original price is 4341.25. Estimated price are higher than the actual prices, indicating potential overestimation by the model.

In 2021-22 and 2022-23, the estimated prices are relatively closer to the actual prices, indicating that the model's accuracy improves in these years.

Despite some deviations, the estimated prices follow the general trend of the actual prices, indicating that the model is capturing the overall movement in spot prices reasonably well.

As per table 4 shows Regression Coefficient of area is -1.22 and t value is -1.86. The negative coefficient suggests that an increase in area is associated with a decrease in spot prices. However, the t value (-1.86) is suggesting that while there is a potential effect, it is not strongly

This analysis provides a comprehensive understanding of how spot prices, future prices, and delivered quantity of guar gum vary over time and their inter-relationships. This information is valuable for market analysis, pricing strategies, and logistical planning.

The impact of arrivals on prices

For achieving the third objective, which is to examine the impact of arrivals on futures prices for selected commodity (Guar gum) multiple regression analysis is performed. This method quantifies the relationship between arrivals and futures prices by modelling the influence of two key independent variables: the area under cultivation and the production levels of these commodities

Estimated spot market price of Guar seed from AGMARK (2015–2023)

To address the objective of examining the impact of arrivals (i.e., area and production of Guar seed) on prices at AGMARK, we need to analyse two sets of data i.e. original and estimated Prices of Guar seed. This shows the actual and estimated future prices of guar gum over various years. Second set of data shows impact of Area and Production on prices of Guar seed, this includes regression coefficients that measure how area and production influence prices at AGMARK.

The table 3 shows the actual versus estimated spot market prices over various years. The estimated prices generally follow the trend of the actual prices but show some deviations. In 2015-16, 2016-17, 2017-18, and 2018-19, the original prices are 3662.91, 3080.28, 3431.04, 3998.21 respectively. In 2015-16, 2016-17, 2017-18, and 2018-19, the estimated prices are 3558.66, 3626.68, 3422.63 & 3428.53 respectively. There are estimated price is lower than the original prices, suggesting that the model may have underestimated the spot prices during these years.

significant. Thus, changes in area might influence spot prices, but this effect is not statistically robust. Regression Coefficient of production is 1.81 and t value is 1.44. The positive coefficient indicates that an increase in production is associated with an increase in spot prices. However, the t value of 1.44 is below the usual significance threshold, suggesting that the effect of production on spot prices is not statistically significant either.

Despite some deviations, the estimated prices follow the general trend of the actual prices, indicating that the model is capturing the overall movement in spot prices reasonably well. The negative relationship with spot prices is not statistically significant. This suggests that changes in area have a potential but not strong impact on spot prices. The positive relationship with spot prices is also not statistically significant, indicating that while production may influence spot prices, the relationship is not

strongly supported by the data. The analysis indicates that while there may be some impact of area and production on spot prices, these effects are not statistically significant based on the regression results.

Estimated Spot Market Price of Guar gum from NCDEX (2015–2023)

To address the objective of examining the impact of arrivals (i.e., area and production of Guar seed) on futures prices at NCDEX, we need to

Table 5: Estimated Spot Market Price of Guar gum from NCDEX (2015–2023)

Year	Original Price	Estimated Price
2015-16	8882.1	8585.86
2016-17	5996.14	8003.27
2017-18	7898.37	7630.85
2018-19	9020.40	7427.09
2019-20	8218.72	7427.09
2020-21	6109.20	8408.12
2021-22	8653.18	8357.06
2022-23	10901.29	8859.04

Table 6: Impact of Area and Production on Guar gum NCDEX Prices

Sr. No.	Particular	Regression coefficient	T value
1	Intercept	8562.09	3.44
2	Area	-1.32	-0.69
3	Production	2.63	0.71

From Table 5 the estimated future prices are close to the actual prices for most years, though there are deviations. For instance, the estimated price for 2016-17 (8003.27) is higher than the actual price (5996.14), suggesting a possible overestimation. The estimated prices follow a similar trend to the actual prices, indicating that the trend estimation model captures the overall pattern of future prices well. Notable deviations are significant deviations occur in 2018-19 and 2019-20 where the estimated prices are constant (7427.09).

From Table 6 the regression coefficient for area is -1.32, indicating that for each unit increase in the area under cultivation, the NCDEX price of Guar gum is expected to decrease by 1.32 units. However, the t-value for area (-0.69) is below the 10% significance threshold (1.646) and is thus not significant at any conventional level, suggests that this coefficient is not statistically significant. Therefore, we do not have strong evidence to conclude that changes in the area under cultivation have a meaningful impact on the NCDEX prices of Guar gum.

The regression coefficient for production is 2.63, Similarly, the t-value for production (0.71) is also below the 10% significance threshold. This suggests that the impact of production on Guar gum prices is not statistically significant at the any levels, indicating no clear evidence that production levels significantly affect the NCDEX prices of Guar gum.

Impact of Area: The negative coefficient for area (-1.32) suggests a potential decrease in prices with increased cultivation area, but the lack of statistical significance means we cannot confidently assert that area changes have a meaningful effect on prices.

Impact of Production: The positive coefficient for production (2.63) suggests a potential increase in prices with higher production levels. However, similar to area, the low t-value indicates that this result is not statistically significant, so we cannot conclusively determine the impact of production on prices.

The regression analysis suggests that while there are theoretical expectations for how area and production might influence Guar gum prices, the current data does not provide statistically significant evidence to confirm these effects. Both area and production coefficients lack statistical significance, indicating that other factors might be influencing Guar gum NCDEX price.

analyse two sets of data: i.e. table.no. 11 and table no.11. 2able no.11 (Original and Estimated Future Prices). This shows the actual and estimated future prices of guar gum over various years. And table no.12 (Impact of Area and Production on Future Prices) this includes regression coefficients that measure how area and production influence futures prices.

Conclusion

The analysis of Guar gum prices and market trends from 2015 to 2023 reveals several key insights:

1. Price Trends: Compound growth rate of spot price and future price quantity is 0.40 and 0.40 respectively Both spot and futures prices of Guar gum showed significant upward movements with high volatility, especially in 2015 and 2021. Future prices closely followed spot price trends but lagged slightly and were less volatile.
2. Delivery Trends: Compound growth rate of delivered quantity -1.1. Delivery rates of Guar gum exhibited a substantial decline, and this trend was statistically significant, reflecting different market dynamics compared to prices. Delivery metrics were not strongly correlated with price fluctuations, indicating other variables influenced deliveries.
3. The Coefficient of Variation (CV) for spot prices showed moderate variability, with the highest variability in 2021. Future prices displayed lower relative variability, while delivery rates had the highest variability, especially in 2016.
4. Volatility was a key characteristic of both spot and futures prices, with peak volatility in 2021. The delivery metric displayed the highest volatility, particularly in 2016, suggesting highly fluctuating delivery patterns.
5. The regression analysis shows that both area and production of Guar seed is not significantly affect on the spot price of Guar seed at AGMARK.
6. Similarly, the regression analysis shows that both area and productions of Guar seed is not significantly affect the future price of Guar gum at NCDEX.

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